

Surface energy balance and surface temperature sensitivity in northern boreal ecosystems

Erkka Rinne*^a, Juha-Pekka Tuovinen^a, Annalea Lohila^{a,b}, and Mika Aurela^a

^a Climate System Research, Finnish Meteorological Institute, P.O. Box 503, 00101, Helsinki, Finland

^b Institute for Atmospheric and Earth System Research/Physics, P.O. Box 64, 00014, University of Helsinki, Finland

14th February 2025

Abstract

Understanding the surface energy balance (SEB) is the key to assessing ecosystems' ability to modify their local climate, and how sensitive they are to changes in their biophysical properties. Atmospheric interactions connect the local phenomena to the global climate system.

We assessed long-term measurement data from six northern boreal sites, three mires and three forests between 67 and 69°N. The results complement existing knowledge by presenting SEB data from areas previously under-represented in the literature. The importance of these high-latitude ecosystems is increasing as areas north of the Arctic Circle have warmed faster than the global average.

Ecosystem available energy was largely defined by the shortwave albedo, which was lower for the darker, coniferous tree-dominated forests than for the open mires. Daily radiative energy did not decrease towards the north during summer as the long polar day compensated for the lower intensity, but lower temperatures during spring and autumn made the seasonal cycles more pronounced than in the more southern areas. The wet, moss-dominated mires were characterised by a low Bowen ratio and high evaporative fraction, low bulk surface resistance to evapotranspiration and high surface layer decoupling. In the forests, evapotranspiration was more tightly controlled by the vegetation, which was sensitive to the soil water content at the pine-dominated sites. High decoupling was observed to occur in the forests during humid conditions.

The surface temperature in both ecosystem types was more sensitive to changes in their surface biophysical properties than to their meteorological drivers.

Keywords: surface energy balance, boreal ecosystems, land surface temperature, surface biophysical properties

*Corresponding author: erkka.rinne@fmi.fi, tel. +358 50 345 7411

1 Introduction

Boreal ecosystems between 50 and 70°N cover 1.4×10^7 km², i.e. one third of the forested areas of the world (Wieder et al., 2006). They are an important part of the global climate system (Chapin et al., 2000), and, while covering only about 2–3 % of the global surface area, their importance has increased due to climate change. The area north of the Arctic Circle (66.5°N) has warmed nearly four times as fast as the globe on average (Rantanen et al., 2022), and thus changes in the boreal biome, especially in its northern parts, are inevitable.

The boreal zone can be defined both climatically and by its characteristic vegetation. According to Walter (1985; see Wieder et al., 2006), the boreal zone lies where mean daily temperatures above 10 °C occur 30–120 days a year and the cold season lasts from six to eight months. Climatic gradients within the boreal zone lead to differences in vegetation and its productivity (Solantie, 2005).

Extensive conifer-dominated forests characterise the boreal zone, giving way to treeless tundra in the north and being replaced by deciduous broadleaf forests or grasslands in the south (Larsen, 1980; see Wieder et al., 2006). While most of the boreal zone is covered by evergreen forests on mineral soils, approximately one quarter of it is peatland (Wieder et al., 2006), and the boreal zone hosts the largest concentrations of wetlands globally (Lafleur, 2008). Mires form in areas where precipitation exceeds evapotranspiration (ET) (Wieder et al., 2006; Lafleur, 2008) creating conditions that potentially lead to the formation of peat as net ecosystem production has exceeded decomposition rates for a long time.

Surface energy balance (SEB) describes the division of incoming radiation energy into heat fluxes to the atmosphere and soil. The biophysical properties of the surface, such as aerodynamic roughness, albedo and vegetation type, coverage and height as well as soil moisture, affect the SEB and effectively create a local climate represented by, e.g. the surface temperature (T_s), which is a central variable of the SEB and a key factor for the functioning of the local ecosystem. Higher albedo leads to more solar radiation being reflected and less energy being available at the surface, thus corresponding to a lower T_s . The partitioning of radiative energy into sensible and latent heat is an important controller of T_s due to evaporative cooling (Li and Wang, 2019). Rougher surfaces create more turbulence enabling transport of heat away from the surface, which lowers the T_s .

The surface properties are strongly affected by abrupt land cover and land management changes, such as intensive logging and wetland restoration, and they can also respond gradually to climate change. Changes in the surface properties lead to changes in the local climate and, through atmospheric interactions, also to non-local changes in areas not undergoing any surface changes (Winckler et al., 2019). To understand how ecosystems modify their local climate in terms of e.g. temperature and humidity, it is crucial to understand the SEB and how the surface properties affect it.

While the SEB of boreal ecosystems has been investigated earlier, these studies have focused on either European hemiboreal and southern boreal sites south of 65°N (Launiainen, 2010; Runkle et al., 2014; Alekseychik

53 et al., 2018) or on Arctic locations in north-west Canada in areas underlain with continuous permafrost (Eaton
54 et al., 2001; Graveline et al., 2024). To complement the knowledge gained in these studies, we analysed long-
55 term data from six pristine ecosystems in the northern boreal zone, located in the north of Finland between
56 67 and 69°N. These data included the sensible and latent heat fluxes measured with the eddy covariance (EC)
57 technique, key radiation components and soil heat fluxes. From these data, we determined the diel and seasonal
58 variation of the SEB components along with common indicators for energy partitioning and ecosystem–atmosphere
59 coupling. Furthermore, we assessed how these ecosystems would respond to changes in surface parameters and
60 the meteorological drivers of the SEB, and how different surface characteristics lead to different responses in T_s .
61 The specific research questions were: 1) What are the key differences between and among northern boreal mires
62 and forests in terms of SEB? How do they compare to similar ecosystems in more southern or northern areas? 2)
63 Which surface biophysical properties contribute to the differences between ecosystems' T_s ? 3) How sensitive are
64 T_s to changes in the surface properties and meteorological drivers?

65 **2 Methodology**

66 **2.1 Study sites**

67 Three pristine mires and three unmanaged forests located in northern Finland were included in the study (Fig. 1).
68 The six sites are located in three distinct areas, a mire and a nearby forest in each. The areas and sites are described
69 briefly below, and more details are given in Tables 1 and 2.

70 The boreal zone can be further divided into southern, middle and northern subzones based on the mean air
71 temperature. A usable metric is the mean annual biotemperature, i.e. mean of air temperatures between 0 and
72 30 °C, which in the northern boreal zone is 3.25–4.25 °C (Tuhkanen, 1984).

73 **Sodankylä**

74 Sodankylä is located 100 km north of the Arctic Circle and is the southernmost of the three areas. The area
75 has warmed 0.7 °C since the previous climate reference period (mean annual temperature during 1981–2010 was
76 –0.4 °C, Pirinen et al., 2012), and the mean annual biotemperature has risen to 4.3 °C (Table 1). According to
77 the classification by Tuhkanen (1984), Sodankylä now belongs to the middle boreal zone. However, as changes in
78 vegetation succeed slowly, the sites in the Sodankylä area can still be considered representative of northern boreal
79 ecosystems.

80 The *Halssiaapa* mire (SoM) is a mesotrophic fen representing a typical northern aapa mire with a pattern of
81 wetter flarks and drier strings (Linkosalmi et al., 2016). The vegetation is mainly low (*Carex* spp., *Menyanthes*
82 *trifoliata*, *Andromeda polifolia*, *Betula nana*, *Vaccinium oxycoccos*, *Sphagnum* spp.) and there are only some trees

Figure 1: Locations of the site areas in northern Finland. Each dot represents a mire and a forest site within 0.3–2 km of each other. (Background map made with Natural Earth.)

83 (*Betula pubescens*, *Pinus sylvestris*) on the drier parts.

84 The Sodankylä forest (SoF) is a Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) stand (Thum et al., 2007) located 0.97 km south-
 85 west of SoM. The soil type is podzolic sandy till with an average fraction of fine material of 4.6 % (0–40 cm depth).
 86 The age of the trees was approximately 100 years, and the sparse ground vegetation consisted of lichens (73 %),
 87 mosses (12 %) and ericaceous shrubs (15 %) (Thum et al., 2007).

88 Pallas

89 The Pallas area is characterised by large fells and generally higher elevation than the other sites.

90 The Lompolojänkkä mire (PaM) is an open, mesotrophic sedge fen (Aurela et al., 2009). A small stream
 91 flows through it in the SSE–NNE direction (approximately 15 m from the EC measurement stand), and the site is
 92 characterised by a high water table level throughout the year. Vegetation is dominated by *Betula nana*, *Menyanthes*
 93 *trifoliata*, *Salix lapponum* and *Carex* spp., and there are also some low shrubs, mainly *Andromeda polyfolia* and
 94 *Vaccinium oxycoccos*. Moss coverage was patchy (57 %) and consisted mostly of *Sphagnum* mosses and some
 95 brown mosses in low amounts (Aurela et al., 2015). The peat depth was up to 2.5 m at the centre of the fen (Aurela
 96 et al., 2015).

97 The Kenttäröva forest (PaF) lies on a hill-top plateau (Aurela et al., 2015) 1.8 km south-east of PaM. The soil
 98 type is podzolic sandy till with a fraction of fine material of 23.2 % (20–40 cm depth; Lohila et al., 2016). The main
 99 species is the Norway spruce (*Picea abies*), but there are also some deciduous trees (*Betula pubescens*, *Populus*
 100 *tremula*, *Salix caprea*). The age of the trees was between 80 and 240 years, and the ground floor was covered
 101 mainly by *Vaccinium myrtillus*, *Empetrum nigrum*, *V. vitis-idaea* and forest mosses *Pleurozium* sp., *Hylocomium*
 102 sp. and *Dicranum* sp. (Aurela et al., 2015).

103 **Kaamanen**

104 Kaamanen is the northernmost area of the three, located about 300 km north of the Arctic Circle, where climate
105 turns subarctic.

106 The *Kaamanen* mire (KaM) is an open flark fen, also a typical example of the aapa mire region (Aurela et al.,
107 1998). The area near the EC measurement mast is dominated by a pattern of strings and flarks with a horizontal
108 scale of a few metres. The height of the strings, which cover approximately one third of the surface area, is
109 0.3–0.8 m, and the vegetation follows this microtopography due to differences in wetness and nutrients. Thin
110 lenses of ice can remain inside the strings until late summer (Aurela et al., 2001). A small river flows across the
111 fen to the north and east from the EC measurement, closest at about 120 m. The wet flarks were dominated by
112 brown mosses and sedges, while the uppermost parts of the ridges hosted forest mosses (*Pleurozium schreberi*)
113 and Ericales species (*Vaccinium* spp., *Rubus chamaemorus*, *Empetrum nigrum*) and their wetter margins were
114 covered by *Sphagnum* mosses, sedges, *Betula nana* and *Andromeda polifolia* (Maanavilja et al., 2011). A few
115 *Betula pubescens* and *Pinus sylvestris* trees were found in the driest places of the fen (Heiskanen et al., 2021). The
116 average peat depth was about 1 m (Aurela et al., 1998).

117 The *Kaamanen forest* (KaF), located 0.30 km west of KaM on sandy podzol, is dominated by Scots pine (*Pinus*
118 *syvestris*) with a few downy birch (*Betula pubescens*) trees (Heiskanen et al., 2023). The field layer was dominated
119 by dwarf shrubs (*Vaccinium vitis-idaea*, *Calluna vulgaris*), and the ground was covered by mosses and lichens
120 (Heiskanen et al., 2023).

121 **2.2 Measurement data**

122 Fluxes of sensible heat and water vapour were determined using the EC technique. Measurement heights are given
123 in Table 2, and Table 1 shows the periods from which good-quality flux data were available. Table A.1 lists the sonic
124 anemometers and infrared gas analysers employed. The sampling frequency of EC signals at all sites was 10 Hz,
125 and the 30-min fluxes were calculated with an in-house software application following standard EC procedures,
126 including block averaging, double coordinate rotation, lag determination by cross-correlation maximisation and
127 correction for high-frequency flux losses with empirical transfer functions; for details, see the original publications
128 listed in Table 1.

129 The flux datasets were quality controlled following the methodology by Mauder et al. (2013). A low-turbulence
130 friction velocity (u_*) threshold was estimated for SoM using the method described by Papale et al. (2006) and
131 implemented by Vekuri and Rinne (2023). For the other sites, we used the threshold values determined in previous
132 studies (Table 1).

133 The fluxes were filtered excluding poor-quality data (flag value 2 in the 0-1-2 system; Mauder and Foken, 2004)
134 and the low-turbulence cases (Table 2). At PaF, also the data collected during high wind speeds with $u_* > 0.6 \text{ m s}^{-1}$

Table 1: Overview of the study areas and measurement sites. The last letter of the site label identifies the ecosystem type, mire (M) or forest (F). The site names and identifiers (if applicable) correspond to those used within the FLUXNET or ICOS networks. Summer refers to June–August. The source of data is the reference mentioned or own work if not otherwise specified. Data period refers to the date range when good quality data for all SEB components were available. A dash (—) indicates a not measured or not applicable value.

	Sodankylä		Pallas		Kaamanen	
Reference climate point (WMO code)	Sodankylä Tähtelä (02836)		Muonio Alamuonio (02823)		Inari Ivalo airport (02807)	
Mean temperature (°C; annual, summer) ^a	0.3, 13.1		−0.6, 12.4		0.3, 12.3	
Daily mean temp. above 0, 5, 10 °C (d) ^a	179, 134, 87		172, 130, 81		179, 132, 80	
Mean annual biotemperature (°C)	4.3		4.1		4.1	
Precipitation (mm; annual, summer) ^a	543, 192		532, 200		485, 210	
Snow cover duration (d; months) ^a	200, Oct–Apr		180, Nov–Apr		180, Nov–Apr	
Length of shortest day, polar night and polar day	24 min, 0 d, 44 d		0 min, 25 d, 52 d		0 min, 43 d, 64 d	
	SoM	SoF	PaM	PaF	KaM	KaF
Name (site id.)	Halssiaapa	Sodankylä (FI-Sod)	Lompolojänkkä (FI-Lom)	Kenttäröva (FI-Ken)	Kaamanen (FI-Kaa)	Kaamanen forest
Location	67.369°N, 26.654°E, 180 m a.s.l.	67.362°N, 26.639°E, 179 m a.s.l.	67.997°N, 24.209°E, 269 m a.s.l.	67.987°N, 24.243°E, 347 m a.s.l.	69.140°N, 27.271°E, 155 m a.s.l.	69.141°N, 27.263°E, 155 m a.s.l.
Reference	Linkosalmi et al., 2016	Thum et al., 2007	Aurela et al., 2009	Aurela et al., 2015	Aurela et al., 1998	Heiskanen et al., 2023
Description	open mesotrophic fen	Scots pine forest	open mesotrophic fen	Norway spruce forest	open mesotrophic fen	Scots pine forest
Tree density (ha ^{−1} ; main sp., deciduous)	—	2100, —	—	643, 68	—	545, 103
Leaf area index (m ² m ^{−2}) [*]	0.70 ^b	1.8	1.3	2.0 (0.1)	0.70 ^c	2.0
Mean annual wind speed (m s ^{−1}) ^e	3.0	3.0	3.1	3.8 [¶]	3.2	3.2
Data period	2013-06-01/ 2022-12-12	2018-09-20/ 2023-12-19	2017-07-18/ 2019-12-31	2010-09-01/ 2021-02-25	1998-05-25/ 2019-05-03	2017-06-11/ 2019-11-10

^a Normal period 1990–2020; Jokinen et al., 2021

^b Pang et al., 2023

^c Aurela et al., 2001

^e Finnish Meteorological Institute, potential wind speed at the closest weather station, period 2014–2023

^{*} Summer maximum of one-sided (half total) LAI. Mires: only vascular plants. Forests: only trees, secondary species in parentheses.

[¶] From 2016-07-22

Table 2: Details on the measurement setups. Values without uncertainty are from previous studies, see references in Table 1. Zero-plane displacement height is given only for the summer months (June–August).

Site	Vegetation height (m)	Zero-plane displacement height (m, mean±s.d.) [§]	EC measurement height (m)	Low-turbulence u_* threshold (m s^{-1})	Included wind directions (°)	Air temp. and humidity measurement height(s) (m)
SoM	0.4	0.3	6.5	0.16 ± 0.04 [¶]	(281.5, 258.5)	3.0 (1.8 before 2014-07-18)
PaM	0.4	0.2	3.0	0.10	[300, 10], [100, 170]	3.0
KaM	0.3	0.5	5.0	0.12	(297, 222)	3.0
SoF	12.0	9.8 ± 0.7	25.0	0.25	[322.5, 277.5]	1.0, 3.2, 6.6, 10.1, 13.8, 19.1, 25.1
PaF	13.0	8.2 ± 0.5	23.0	0.25	[0, 360]	2.0, 20.0
KaF	11.0	5.7 ± 0.5	14.0	0.24	[250, 65]	— [†]

[§] Standard deviation across wind sectors

[¶] Mean \pm standard error of 100 times bootstrapped estimate

[†] No measurements

135 were discarded because of the strong response of observed fluxes to turbulence at high wind speeds (Aurela et al.,
 136 2015). Fluxes from sectors which did not represent the main ecosystem at the site were excluded (Table 2). Table 3
 137 shows the flux data coverages before and after filtering.

Table 3: Sensible heat (H) and water vapour flux (E) data coverages before and after filtering (%). Last two columns show coverages during summer months June–August.

Site	Raw	Filtered (all)		Filtered (JJA)	
		H	E	H	E
SoM	64	38	35	51	50
PaM	95	38	35	43	41
KaM	75	43	39	56	54
SoF	82	45	42	48	48
PaF	84	19	29	39	36
KaF	53	16	10	23	18

138 Additional meteorological measurements included net radiation, incoming (except KaF) and reflected shortwave
 139 radiation, incoming longwave radiation, air temperature and relative humidity (except KaF), atmospheric pressure,
 140 soil heat flux (7 cm below ground at PaF and KaM, 7.5 cm at SoF and KaF, 10 cm at SoM), water table depth
 141 (WTD, only mires) and soil water content (SWC, only forests, 10 cm below ground). WTD at the forest sites was
 142 assumed to be usually deep enough to have a negligible impact on the vegetation. At SoF and PaF, temperature and
 143 humidity were measured both below and above the canopy (Table 2). Meteorological data were quality controlled
 144 using physical limits, median absolute deviation for statistical outliers and manual screening. Meteorological data
 145 coverage was in general better than that of the fluxes and was not a limiting factor to the analysis. The data were
 146 gap-filled using linear interpolation (with limited number of points) or nearby measurements with potential linear
 147 relationships or a combination of these (Appendix B).

148 Air temperature and humidity above the forest canopy at KaF were estimated from the sonic temperature
 149 and the humidity obtained from the fast-response gas analyser, respectively, because no precision measurements

150 were available (Appendix B). Also, as only reflected shortwave radiation was measured at KaF, net radiation was
 151 calculated from the incoming radiation measurements at KaM and outgoing longwave radiation was estimated
 152 using the air temperature.

153 2.3 Surface energy balance

154 The surface energy balance can be written as

$$R_n - G = H + L_e E + S_H + S_{LE} \quad (1)$$

155 where R_n is the net radiative energy (flux density, W m^{-2}), G the soil heat flux, H the sensible heat flux, L_e the
 156 latent heat of vaporization at current air temperature (e.g. Bolton, 1980; J kg^{-1}) and E the water vapour flux
 157 ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). The term $L_e E$ is the latent heat flux. Other terms, such as heat storage in the biomass, were ignored.
 158 The left-hand side of Eq. (1) is referred to as the available energy, AE. In Eq. (1), we follow the micrometeorological
 159 sign convention where R_n is defined positive if the surface gains energy, the other fluxes are positive when directed
 160 away from the surface and the storage changes are positive when energy is stored within the canopy.

161 The changes in the sensible and latent heat stored below the flux measurement, S_H and S_{LE} , respectively, were
 162 calculated from the changes in air temperature and humidity, respectively, following Haverd et al. (2007):

$$S_H = \int_0^{z_m^{\text{EC}}} \rho_d c_p \frac{dT_a(z)}{dt} dz \quad (2)$$

$$S_{LE} = \int_0^{z_m^{\text{EC}}} \rho_d L_e \frac{ds_v(z)}{dt} dz, \quad (3)$$

163 where z_m^{EC} is the EC flux measurement height above ground, ρ_d the density of dry air, c_p the specific heat of dry air
 164 at constant pressure, $T_a(z)$ the air temperature at height z and $s_v(z)$ the corresponding mass mixing ratio of water
 165 vapour to dry air derived from the measured relative humidity. The integral was calculated using the trapezoidal
 166 rule (Python function `numpy.trapz`), and the time derivative was approximated by $\frac{d}{dt} \approx \frac{\Delta}{\Delta t}$, where $\Delta t = 30$ min.
 167 With only single-level measurements available from the mires, the vertical profiles of temperature and humidity
 168 were assumed constant below z_m^{EC} .

169 The Bowen ratio is defined as the ratio between sensible and latent heat flux, i.e. $\beta = H/L_e E$, and the
 170 evaporative fraction as $\text{EF} = L_e E / (H + L_e E)$. In the latter, dividing by the sum of the turbulent fluxes instead of
 171 $R_n - G$, which is also a commonly used practice, we avoid the differences between the flux footprint and the other
 172 measurements as well as any imbalance between AE and the turbulent fluxes. Both β and EF were calculated using
 173 daytime (09:30–14:30 local standard time, LT) means of the relevant SEB components when $|L_e E| \geq 5 \text{ W m}^{-2}$
 174 and $H + L_e E \geq 50 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ to exclude events with very small E or AE, respectively.

175 Monthly mean energy balance components were calculated as the mean of daily means with the minimum data
176 coverage of 20 % required for any averaging period.

177 2.4 Energy balance closure

178 In practice, measurements of the SEB components typically leave imbalance to Eq. (1), due to various reasons
179 including the energy terms not measured (e.g. snowmelt, advection) and mismatch of the turbulent flux footprint
180 and the other terms (e.g. Foken, 2008). Assuming most of the imbalance is due to the underestimation of the
181 turbulent heat fluxes, energy balance closure (EBC) is defined as the ratio between their sum and the sum of the
182 other SEB terms. Closures are typically of the order of 80 % (Wilson et al., 2002; Mauder et al., 2024) but are
183 dependent on the ecosystem type and season (Cui and Chui, 2019).

184 We calculated the EBCs as the ratio between $H + L_e E$ and $AE - S_H - S_{LE}$. Because the data were sparse, the
185 ratios were calculated from the monthly mean diurnal cycles of each SEB component. Alternatively, the cycle was
186 calculated from all data belonging to the same calendar month if not enough data were available. Closures were
187 calculated for each full year and the summer months June–August separately.

188 2.5 Surface biophysical properties

189 We considered the key biophysical properties affecting the SEB of a terrestrial ecosystem: albedo, surface
190 roughness, vegetation and water availability.

191 Shortwave reflectivity, albedo, was calculated as the ratio between the reflected (S_{\uparrow}) and incoming (S_{\downarrow})
192 shortwave radiation, $\alpha = S_{\uparrow}/S_{\downarrow}$. This ratio was computed from the mean daytime values of the radiation
193 components including only periods when $S_{\downarrow}, S_{\uparrow} > 0$ and $S_{\downarrow} > S_{\uparrow}$.

194 We estimated the surface roughness length, z_0 , for each 22.5° wind sector separately from the equation for
195 wind speed u

$$u(z^{EC}) = \frac{u_*}{\kappa} \left[\ln \frac{z^{EC}}{z_0} - \Psi_m \left(\frac{z^{EC}}{L} \right) \right], \quad (4)$$

196 where $\kappa = 0.4$ is the von Kármán constant, u_* the friction velocity, Ψ_m the stability correction function for
197 momentum (Dyer and Hicks, 1970) and L the Obukhov length (Stull, 1988). The equation was evaluated at
198 $z^{EC} \equiv z_m^{EC} - d$, i.e. the effective EC measurement height above the zero-plane displacement height d . The
199 resulting z_0 time series was filtered using a 7-day rolling window median of daytime values because z_0 of vegetated
200 surfaces mainly varies with plant phenology. The smoothing was performed for each wind sector separately and
201 the minimum data coverage for each window was 5 %. For the forest sites, we estimated d based on flux–gradient
202 and flux–variance similarity relationships to account for differences in the canopy height in different wind sectors
203 (Table 2). The methodology is described in Appendix C. For the mire sites, where vegetation was low, the values
204 determined in previous studies were applied.

205 Effects of vegetation and water availability were expressed using the bulk surface resistance to evapotranspira-
 206 tion, r_s . We employed the big-leaf model for the turbulent fluxes, which were parametrised using their resistance
 207 analogies (e.g. Lee, 2018):

$$H = \rho_d c_p \frac{T_s - T_a(z)}{r_h(z)} \quad (5)$$

208 and

$$E = \rho_d \frac{s_v^*(T_s) - s_v(z)}{r_v(z) + r_s}, \quad (6)$$

209 where T_s is the temperature of the big-leaf surface and s_v^* is the saturation mass mixing ratio of water vapour (a
 210 function of temperature; Bolton, 1980). In the divisors, $r_h(z)$ and $r_v(z)$ are the aerodynamic resistances to heat
 211 and water vapour transfer to height z , respectively. We evaluated Eqs. (5) and (6) at $z \equiv z_m - d$, where z_m is the
 212 temperature and humidity measurement height above the ground.

213 The aerodynamic resistance to heat transfer r_h is given by

$$r_h(z) = \frac{1}{\kappa u_*} \left[\ln \frac{z}{z_0} + \ln \frac{z_0}{z_{0,h}} - \Psi_h \left(\frac{z}{L} \right) \right], \quad (7)$$

214 where Ψ_h is the stability correction function for heat (Dyer and Hicks, 1970) and $z_{0,h}$ the thermal roughness length.
 215 For many natural surfaces, $\ln \left(\frac{z_0}{z_{0,h}} \right) \approx 2$ (Garratt, 1994), which we used for all the sites.

216 The bulk surface resistance, r_s , was solved from Eq. (6) after solving T_s from Eq. (5), which essentially
 217 represents the same footprint as that of E . In a number of previous similar studies (Launiainen, 2010; Runkle
 218 et al., 2014; Alekseychik et al., 2018; Helbig et al., 2020; Graveline et al., 2024), r_s was solved from the
 219 Penman–Monteith equation, which utilises a linear approximation of the water vapour saturation pressure at T_s .
 220 Here, no such approximation was needed. We assumed that the aerodynamic resistances to heat and water vapour
 221 turbulent transfer are approximately equal, i.e. $r_h \approx r_v \equiv r$.

222 We assessed the sensitivity of bulk surface conductance (r_s^{-1}) to ambient vapour pressure deficit (D) in abundant
 223 light conditions ($S_{\downarrow} > 300 \text{ W m}^{-2}$) and temperatures above zero using the model

$$r_s^{-1} = r_{s,\text{ref}}^{-1} - m \times \ln(D/D_0), \quad (8)$$

224 where $r_{s,\text{ref}}$ is the reference resistance at $D_0 = 1 \text{ kPa}$ and m a sensitivity parameter (Oren et al., 1999). The model
 225 was fit to each month of data to account for variations in environmental conditions and especially SWC potentially
 226 affecting $r_{s,\text{ref}}$ (Launiainen, 2010). To equally weight both high and low D events, the full range of D observations
 227 was divided into ten equal-width bins, and the model was fitted to the median 30-min D and r_s^{-1} of each bin using
 228 ordinary least squares. To exclude erroneous values, r_s was limited to the interval $[20, 1000] \text{ s m}^{-1}$.

229 The decoupling factor (Jarvis and McNaughton, 1986) expresses how well the conditions at the big-leaf surface

230 are connected to the free airstream in the atmospheric surface layer at height z . It is given by

$$\Omega(z) = \frac{\Delta/\gamma + 1}{\Delta/\gamma + 1 + r_s/r(z)}, \quad (9)$$

231 where Δ is the derivative of saturation vapour pressure with respect to temperature (Pa K^{-1}) given by the
232 Clausius–Clapeyron equation and $\gamma = p_d c_p / (0.622 L_e)$ is the psychrometric constant (Pa K^{-1}). In a fully coupled
233 state when $r_s \gg r$ and $\Omega = 0$, ET is limited by the surface and vegetative control. At full decoupling when $\Omega = 1$,
234 ET is limited by AE and turbulent mixing ($r_s \ll r$). Because of the different instrumentation heights, Ω was
235 evaluated at the reference height $z_{\text{ref}} = 20$ m allowing comparisons between the sites.

236 We filtered the data to exclude points with low EBC and thus possibly unreliable estimates of the turbulent
237 fluxes. We found that in stable conditions with the Monin–Obukhov stability parameter $\zeta \equiv z^{EC}/L > 0.01$, EBC
238 averaged over all sites dropped below 60%, and in very unstable conditions with $\zeta < -1$, there was much higher
239 variance in the EBC. Thus only unstable and near-neutral conditions with $-1 \leq \zeta \leq 0.01$ were considered in the
240 parts of the analysis that involved the flux parametrisations.

241 Furthermore, we assumed that any surface energy imbalance after the above-mentioned filtering was caused
242 by the underestimation of the turbulent energy fluxes. Sensible and latent heat fluxes were therefore corrected by
243 distributing the imbalance to both H and $L_e E$ assuming that the Bowen ratio is correct (Blanken et al., 1997).
244 Other commonly used methods include attributing the imbalance to only one of the turbulent heat fluxes (Twine
245 et al., 2000; Ingwersen et al., 2011), completely to dispersive fluxes (De Roo and Mauder, 2018) or according to
246 the ratio of the sensible heat flux and the buoyancy flux (Charuchittipan et al., 2014). The Bowen ratio method
247 has been shown to result in the smallest differences between simulated true and measured fluxes for both H and
248 $L_e E$ also in situations with vertical advection (Zhou et al., 2023). Following Pastorello et al. (2020), the correction
249 factors were calculated as the median of the inverse EBC in a 31-day moving window including only 09:30–14:30
250 and 21:30–02:30 LT. The corrected turbulent heat fluxes were calculated by multiplying by the correction factors,
251 which were restricted to the closed interval $[1, 2]$. We also analysed the sensitivity of the results to the correction
252 procedure (Appendix E).

253 Liao et al. (2018) found that aggregating the input data to daily resolution improved the accuracy of flux
254 parametrisations, and we adopted this approach, which also limited the noise in the 30-min data. All input data
255 was first limited to daytime, 09:30–14:30 LT, and then averaged to daily resolution using arithmetic mean. The
256 presented results use this averaging unless otherwise specified.

257 **2.6 Surface temperature and its sensitivity**

258 In order to study the sensitivity of T_s to changes in the surface properties and meteorological drivers, Eq. (1) needs
259 to be written out using T_s as a variable. The soil heat flux and the heat storage change fluxes were treated as

260 driving variables, although strictly speaking they would also be functions of T_s . For simplicity, these were summed
261 together as the total storage flux $S_{\text{tot}} \equiv G + S_H + S_{LE}$.

262 Net radiation can be written out as

$$R_n = (1 - \alpha)S_{\downarrow} + \varepsilon(L_{\downarrow} - \sigma T_s^4), \quad (10)$$

263 where ε is the surface emissivity, L_{\downarrow} the incoming longwave radiation (W m^{-2}) and σ the Stefan–Boltzmann
264 constant. We used an emissivity of 0.95 for all the sites, a value given by Tao et al. (2013) for both evergreen
265 needleleaf forests and wooded wetlands. Generally, emissivity changes play a minor role compared to differences
266 in albedo (Juang et al., 2007; Yu et al., 2022).

267 The surface temperature T_s was then solved iteratively from the parametrised SEB equation

$$(1 - \alpha)S_{\downarrow} + \varepsilon(L_{\downarrow} - \sigma T_s^4) - S_{\text{tot}} = \rho_d c_p \frac{T_s - T_a}{r} + L_e \rho_d \frac{s_v^*(T_s) - s_v}{r + r_s} \quad (11)$$

268 using the secant method (Python function `scipy.optimize.newton`) with a tolerance of $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ W m}^{-2}$ and a
269 maximum of 50 iterations. The air temperature T_a was assumed independent of T_s , i.e. no feedback effects were
270 considered.

271 The change in mean T_s when changing the other variables of Eq. (11) was done separately for spring, summer
272 and autumn. The time series of a variable was altered by forcing its time average to a new value: positive variables
273 were scaled with the ratio of the new and the original average and S_{tot} by adding their difference. The new averages
274 were varied between the minimum and the maximum seasonal averages over all the sites of the same ecosystem
275 type and years. Here, the means of the resistances were calculated as harmonic means, and r_s was limited as in
276 fitting Eq. (8).

277 During snowmelt, albedo (α) decreases rapidly within a few weeks, especially at open mires (Peräkylä et al.,
278 2025). The timing of snowmelt thus has a major impact on the mean α and T_s during spring. We therefore also
279 investigated the effect of shifting the α time series in time by a number of days to simulate earlier or later snowmelt
280 during spring or snowfall during autumn. Before shifting, the data were gap-filled with monthly values averaged
281 over the whole dataset of each site.

282 **2.7 Statistical testing**

283 We tested if the SEB components, surface properties or other diagnostic variables were different (1) among the
284 sites of the same ecosystem type, (2) between mires and forests combined and (3) between the mire and the
285 forest within each study area. Since most of the variables were not normally distributed, we used the non-
286 parametric Kruskal–Wallis H test (using the Python function `scipy.stats.kruskal`). As a post-hoc test for

287 the multiple comparisons among the three sites of the same ecosystem type, we applied the Conover–Iman test
288 with the Holm–Bonferroni method for correcting the p -values (using `scikit_posthocs.posthoc_conover`
289 with `p_adjust='holm'`). To test if mires and forests differ in any of the variables, we tested the combined
290 sample of the variable from all the mires against that from all the forests using the Brunner Munzel test
291 (`scipy.stats.brunnermunzel` with `distribution='normal'`) because of its ability to compare samples
292 with unequal variance. The same test was used for each variable between the two ecosystems in an area. The null
293 hypothesis was that the distributions are equal, and the significance level was chosen to be 5 %.

294 For non-normal distributions, we used the median and the interquartile range ($IQR = Q_3 - Q_1$) as the descriptive
295 statistics of location and scale, respectively. To compare the variance between datasets of different locations and
296 scales, the quartile coefficient of dispersion ($QCD = (Q_3 - Q_1)/(Q_3 + Q_1)$) was used.

297 **3 Results and discussion**

298 **3.1 Energy balance closure**

299 Based on the EBCs, our measurement data are of similar quality as those employed in corresponding previous
300 studies and include the relevant SEB components (Appendix D). However, PaM stands out with its anomalously
301 low EBC even during the growing season, and thus the results for this site should be interpreted with caution.

302 **3.2 SEB components and energy partitioning**

303 During summer days (June–August, 09:30–14:30 LT), the mean total incoming radiation was 743 ± 5 , 722 ± 4 and
304 $703 \pm 3 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ (\pm standard error) for the three areas, Sodankylä, Pallas and Kaamanen, respectively, and decreased
305 towards the north, as expected. The total radiation was, on average, almost equally split between the short- and
306 longwave components, but the latter had much smaller variation (Figs. 2a and 2b). However, the 24-h incoming
307 radiative energies during the summer months did not significantly differ among the areas (Table 4). Thus, it seems
308 that the long polar days at the northern sites compensate for the somewhat lower radiation intensity during the
309 daytime.

310 The forests had a higher average R_n , i.e. absorbed more radiation energy, than the mires (Fig. 2c). Neither the
311 daytime nor 24-h average R_n was significantly different among ecosystems of the same type in different areas, and
312 consequently, the same applies to AE (Fig. 2e). The total 24-h R_n in the forests during summer was not lower than
313 that observed in a more southern Scots pine forest (Hyytiälä, 61.9°N , 24.3°E), where the July–August average R_n
314 was $10.0 \pm 0.9 \text{ MJ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (Launiainen, 2010). Alekseychik et al. (2018) reported mean annual growing season
315 (May–October) R_n between 30 and 105 W m^{-2} for two Scots pine-dominated forests at 60.6 – 62.2°N in southern
316 Finland, whereas at our sites the corresponding values were within 90 – 114 W m^{-2} . Alekseychik et al. (2018)

Figure 2: Distributions of summer day (June–August, 9:30–14:30 LT) incoming (a, b) and net radiation (c), ground heat flux (d), ecosystem available energy (e) and total heat storage change (f). The boxes range from the 25th to 75th and whiskers from the 2.5th to 97.5th percentile. The circles show arithmetic means, and the values above the boxes display median and QCD in parentheses. Superscript letters show significantly different groups within the same ecosystem type.

Table 4: Mean daily energy during summer months (June–August) (mean ± standard deviation over the measurement years). Superscript letters show significantly different groups within the ecosystem types.

Site	Incoming radiation (MJ m ⁻² d ⁻¹)		Net radiation (MJ m ⁻² d ⁻¹)	Available energy (MJ m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
	shortwave	longwave		
SoM	16.0 ± 1.2	29.0 ± 0.4 ^a	7.3 ± 1.3	7.0 ± 1.0
PaM	15.3 ± 1.3	28.6 ± 0.4 ^a	7.5 ± 0.9	6.6 ± 2.5
KaM	14.5 ± 2.5	28.2 ± 0.7 ^b	8.1 ± 1.6	6.6 ± 1.3
SoF	15.4 ± 2.3	28.7 ± 0.9	10.8 ± 1.0	10.4 ± 0.7
PaF	16.1 ± 1.5	28.5 ± 0.4	11.3 ± 0.9	10.5 ± 0.7
KaF	14.5 ± 2.5	28.2 ± 0.7	10.9 ± 1.6	10.6 ± 1.7

317 also showed corresponding data for three southern boreal open mires at 61.8–64.2°N with annual growing season
318 average R_n between 25 and 90 $W m^{-2}$, while at our mire sites they were within 43–80 $W m^{-2}$. The albedos were
319 not reported by Alekseychik et al. (2018), but we can assume similar reflectivity at the southern and northern sites
320 based on their vegetation compositions. Moving east to a more continental climate, a fen in northwestern Russia
321 (61.9°N, 50.2°E, 119 m a.s.l.) received more incoming shortwave radiation than any of our sites in June–August,
322 16.8 $MJ m^{-2} d^{-1}$ on average, resulting in a higher R_n of 9.9 $MJ m^{-2} d^{-1}$ (Runkle et al., 2014).

323 In a subarctic black spruce (*Picea mariana*) forest, located at 68.3°N, 133.5°W, 80 m a.s.l. within the continuous
324 permafrost zone in north-west Canada (mean annual temperature -7.8 °C), the 14-day moving average R_n peaked at
325 approximately 175 $W m^{-2}$ at the end of May and decreased to 100 $W m^{-2}$ by early August (Graveline et al., 2024).
326 This differs from PaF, the most similar of our sites, where the monthly mean R_n during June and July was quite
327 stable at $138 \pm 18 W m^{-2}$ (mean \pm standard deviation over all years) even though the summer mean temperatures
328 are almost equal (12.2 °C, Inuvik, Canada; The Meteorological Service of Canada, 2024). Possible reasons for
329 this difference include the annual thawing of the permafrost active layer at the Canadian site, which limits the
330 surface temperatures and thus the emitted longwave radiation, resulting in a higher R_n in early summer (Eugster
331 et al., 2000). The black spruce forest is also quite sparse (LAI = 0.34 $m^2 m^{-2}$) compared to PaF (2.1 $m^2 m^{-2}$), and
332 its springtime albedo was considerably higher than at PaF, which means that more radiation was reflected, leading
333 to a lower net shortwave radiation. This implies that the explanation for the difference must lie in the longwave
334 radiation balance and could be explained by differences in T_s .

335 The ground heat fluxes of the mires were, on average, lower and there were more negative fluxes than at the
336 forest sites (Fig. 2d). All mires had a clear diurnal cycle in G with negative values, i.e. release of heat from the
337 ground, during the early morning (Fig. 3, top row). This can be explained by the high heat capacity of mire soil
338 due to the high WTD. Heat storage changes, S_H and S_{LE} , played practically no role in the mires (Fig. 2f), but they
339 had a clear diurnal cycle in all forests during the summer (Fig. 3, bottom row). The sparser the tree stand was
340 (Table 1), the more pronounced the diurnal cycle of G was and the less pronounced the S_H and S_{LE} cycles were.
341 On the daily scale, S_H and S_{LE} were on average very close to zero.

342 The most notable difference between the mires and the forests was the partitioning of AE into sensible and
343 latent heat. In the mires, latent heat dominated the daytime energy partitioning throughout the growing season as
344 can be seen both from the SEB components (Fig. 4) and the relatively stable daytime Bowen ratio β (Figs. 5a–5c).
345 Among the mires, SoM had the lowest β and the highest EF during summer days (Figs. 5d and 5h). At PaM, based
346 on the high water table (Fig. F.5) and the vegetation composition, we expected a higher share of L_eE and more
347 similar energy partitioning to that of SoM. However, β was higher and EF lower at PaM than at SoM during June.
348 This can be explained by the lower ambient temperature (Table 1 and Fig. F.9) at PaM: the Pearson correlation
349 between T_a and β was -0.54 , -0.48 and -0.28 at SoM, PaM and KaM, respectively. The seasonal cycle of the
350 24-h β was more pronounced at our sites than that observed in the southern boreal mires (Alekseychik et al., 2018),

Figure 3: Mean diurnal cycles of ground heat flux and the heat storage changes during summer months (June–August). The shaded areas span one standard deviation. Note that positive ground heat flux is directed into the soil.

351 with lower values during April and October but higher values from May to September. There was a similar but
 352 less prominent difference compared to the daytime β of a fen in a more continental climate (Runkle et al., 2014).

353 In the forests, sensible heat dominated the daytime partitioning during spring and early summer, with a median
 354 β of 6–8 in March–April (not shown) and around 3 in May (Figs. 5a–5c). The forest vegetation limited transpiration
 355 during its recovery from winter dormancy, but by July (August at SoF) the Bowen ratios were close to one. In
 356 summer, sensible heat also dominated the partitioning during the early hours of the day until the afternoon at SoF,
 357 but not so much at PaF, where average air temperatures were lower (Fig. F.4). At all the forest sites, EF had a clear
 358 seasonal cycle related to soil freezing, liquid water availability and vegetation phenology with the highest values
 359 taking place during the summer (Fig. 5).

360 Energy partitioning in the forests depended on soil moisture, leaf area and tree species. During summer days, β
 361 was the highest at SoF (Fig. 5d), which had the lowest LAI (Table 1) and a sparse understory and thus least potential
 362 for transpiration. These findings are consistent with previous observations of the summertime β of forests of the
 363 same dominant tree species, with a higher LAI leading to lower a β and vice versa. For example, a summertime
 364 average β of 0.62 (Launiainen, 2010) and 0.55 (Alekseychik et al., 2018) have been observed for southern boreal
 365 Scots pine forests with a LAI of $3.5 \text{ m}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}$ and $2.2 \text{ m}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}$, respectively. At a sparse subarctic spruce forest with
 366 a tree LAI of only $0.34 \text{ m}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}$, the summertime median β was around 2 (Graveline et al., 2024) indicating very
 367 low ET due to adaptation to the dry conditions (annual precipitation 245 mm). The two pine-dominated sites, SoF
 368 and KaF, both have sandy podzol soil and thus we can assume that their ecohydrological properties are similar.
 369 SWC was, on average, higher during the summer months at KaF (Fig. F.6), which could explain also partly the
 370 differences in EF.

371 The largest differences in daytime versus 24-h β were observed in September–October when the 24-h β was

Figure 4: Medians of daily mean energy balance components at each site by month. The very small storage change terms are omitted for clarity. The error bars show bootstrapped 95 % confidence intervals, which for some data points are very small or non-existent due to lack of data.

Figure 5: Daytime (09:30–14:30 LT) Bowen ratio (a–c) and evaporative fraction (e–g) by month with solid lines and daytime distributions of the variables in June–August (d and h). Dashed lines show the 24-h Bowen ratio and evaporative fraction. The error bars on the left span 50 % of values. In the right panel box plots, the circles show arithmetic means, and the values above the boxes display median and QCD in parentheses. Superscript letters show significantly different groups within the same ecosystem type.

372 negative at all sites (no data for SoF) due to the rapidly cooling but still evapotranspiring surface (Figs. 5a–5c).
373 For the southern boreal mires and forests located in milder climates, Alekseychik et al. (2018) reported average
374 24-h β that were larger than zero still in October, and Launiainen (2010) showed S_{\downarrow} -weighted weekly average β
375 for a southern boreal pine forest (Hyytiälä) with the interannual median decreasing from around 3 in April to 1 in
376 October. This is also reflected in a longer growing season in the southern boreal zone: temperatures above 5 °C
377 occur on average 177 days a year (interpolated from monthly mean temperatures in Jokioinen Ilmala, WMO 02963;
378 Jokinen et al., 2021).

379 3.3 Surface biophysical properties

380 Differences in albedo (α) explain the majority of the differences in the ecosystem AE between the mires and the
381 forests. Especially during the snow-covered period, October–May, the mires had a much higher α due to the more
382 continuous snow cover (Figs. 6a and 6c) and, consequently, much lower R_n (Fig. 4). The mires had higher α than
383 the forests also during June–August due to the darker coniferous tree canopies (Fig. 7a). In all the mires studied,
384 the annual variation of α was greatest during May, which is explained by the rather rapid snowmelt occurring at
385 different times. At the forest sites, there were no similar abrupt changes in α , but the within-month variation was
386 higher than that in the mires: the median monthly QCD was 0.11 (IQR 0.18) among the forests and 0.07 (0.12)
387 among the mires; this difference was significant ($p < 0.01$). This α variability in the forests can be explained by
388 the temporally and spatially varying snow cover, especially in the tree canopies.

389 There were clear seasonal patterns in α in the mires during the snow-free period with the lowest values observed
390 right after snow melt, after which they increased towards the middle of the summer and decreased again towards
391 the autumn (Fig. F.7). The α minima are associated with the moist and dark bare soil, and the later development
392 can be linked to the growth of annual plants as depicted in phenological time-lapse images available for these sites
393 (Linkosalmi et al., 2016). However, α also increases with the drying of bare soils and *Sphagnum* mosses (Eugster
394 et al., 2000), demonstrated by the stronger correlation between WTL and α at SoM, where the moss coverage was
395 highest, -0.5 during summer, than at PaM and KaM (-0.04 and -0.08 , respectively). Among the mires, SoM
396 stands out with the highest summertime α , but we should note that the S_{\uparrow} measurement at this site was influenced
397 by a single, small birch tree and, thus, may not have exactly represented the dominance of the moss and dwarf
398 shrub vegetation.

399 The aerodynamic roughness length (z_0) was considerably higher in the forests due to their tall and complex
400 canopies compared to the low vegetation and sparse trees in the mires (Fig. 7b). Roughness was also quite constant
401 throughout the year at the forested sites, whereas the mires showed clear seasonal trends with the lowest values
402 associated with the smooth snow cover (Figs. 6d–6f). The lowest z_0 was observed at KaM despite the presence of
403 a pronounced string-flark pattern, which could be expected to generate high aerodynamic roughness. Instead, we

Figure 6: Monthly median albedo and surface roughness length grouped by area. The markers show medians over all years while the error bars span 95% of the values.

Figure 7: Distributions of daytime (9:30–14:30 LT) surface properties in June–August. The boxes range from the 25th to the 75th and whiskers from the 2.5th to the 97.5th percentile. The circles show arithmetic means, and the values above the boxes display median and QCD in parentheses. Superscript letters show significantly different groups within the same ecosystem type.

404 observed a relatively high zero-plane displacement height (Table 2), possibly because the vegetation on the string
 405 tops was sparse. In contrast, the abundant birches in SoM and the relatively tall shrubs near the EC measurement
 406 at PaM increased z_0 compared to a treeless mire.

407 In the mires, where abundant water was usually available and the moss-dominated vegetation had less control
 408 over transpiration, the median summer day r_s were lower than at SoF and PaF (Fig. 7c). There were no significant
 409 differences in the median values among the mires, but at PaM, with the highest vascular plant LAI (Table 1) and
 410 low moss coverage, r_s was clearly more correlated with S_d and D than in the other two mires (Table 5), indicating
 411 stronger control of transpiration by the vegetation. An increasing trend in the monthly median r_s was observed at
 412 SoM in May–October (Fig. 9; $11 \pm 2 \text{ s m}^{-1}$ per month, one-sided $p < 0.01$), but at PaM and KaM there was no
 413 significant trend. WTD decreased at SoM during the summers until mid-September (Fig. F.5), and there was a

Table 5: Pearson correlation coefficients between bulk surface resistance and selected variables during summer days (09:30–14:30 LT, June–August)

Site	SWC	WTD	T_a	D	S_{\downarrow}	R_n
SoM	—	-0.35	0.44	0.43	0.12	0.16
PaM	—	0.02	0.39	0.51	0.42	0.43
KaM	—	-0.02	0.20	0.34	0.01	0.01
SoF	-0.18	—	0.48	0.79	0.63	0.61
PaF	-0.04	—	0.49	0.80	0.67	0.65
KaF	-0.24	—	0.38	0.73	0.80	0.79

414 negative correlation between WTD and r_s (Table 5). The increase in r_s at SoM towards the end of the summer
415 could be explained by the formation of a dry *Sphagnum* layer that prevents transfer of water from below the surface
416 (Alekseychik et al., 2018).

417 At the forested sites with more vegetative control to transpiration, the influence of ambient humidity and
418 incoming shortwave radiation was stronger than in the mires (Table 5). The within-month variation of r_s was also
419 higher in the forests than in the mires during summer (QCDs 0.40 and 0.25, respectively). The median summer
420 day r_s was very low at KaF and not different from that observed at the close-by mire KaM ($p = 0.18$). The low
421 r_s is also reflected in the energy partitioning as low β and high EF (Figs. 5d and 5h). An explanation for the low
422 average β and the lack of high r_s values at KaF is the lack of high D values in the present dataset. During the
423 heatwave and drought event in July 2018 (Heiskanen et al., 2023), for example, the flux data had to be discarded
424 as they were not representative of the forest ecosystem because of wind direction. This underlines the importance
425 of long-term time series that capture the full range of meteorological variation.

426 Bulk surface conductance (r_s^{-1}), shown in Fig. 8 as a function of ambient D during summer, combines both
427 plant physiology and hydrology at the sites. The difference in the reference resistances ($r_{s,\text{ref}}$) between the mires
428 and the forests is clear: the higher values in the forests result from their tighter control of transpiration by plant
429 stomata. Alekseychik et al. (2018) reported reference resistances of 92 and 118 s m^{-1} for a southern boreal and
430 a middle boreal fen, respectively, and our results for the mire sites are of similar magnitude. The sensitivity
431 parameter m for SoM (Fig. 8) was, however, lower than for the two previously presented fens (6 and 5.3 mm s^{-1} ,
432 respectively); this could be explained by the high coverage of mosses, which lack the stomatal response to D , and
433 by the presence of open water surfaces. The highest $r_{s,\text{ref}}$ and m among the mires determined for KaM can be
434 explained by the high proportion of drier strings within it.

435 For southern boreal pine forests, Alekseychik et al. (2018) reported $r_{s,\text{ref}}$ of 185 s m^{-1} for a peatland forest
436 ($\text{LAI} = 2.2 \text{ m}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}$) during May–October and Launiainen (2010) $163 \pm 50 \text{ s m}^{-1}$ for a denser forest on mineral
437 soil during June–August ($3.5 \text{ m}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}$, mean \pm standard deviation over different months). Our results for SoF
438 agree with the previous estimates, but the value for KaF was lower, likely because of the limited data coverage
439 discussed above. LAI may partly explain the different $r_{s,\text{ref}}$ values, but it should be noted that r_s does not scale

Figure 8: Bulk surface conductance (inverse of resistance) versus ambient vapour pressure deficit (D) in ample radiation and non-freezing temperatures (incoming shortwave radiation $> 300 \text{ W m}^{-2}$, air temperature $> 0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) during the summer months (June–August). The model $r_s^{-1} = r_{s,ref}^{-1} - m \times \ln(D/D_0)$ was fitted for each month, and the parameter values shown are the means (\pm standard deviation) over all models. The black line is the predicted conductance using the mean parameter values, and the shaded area covers 95 % of the different models.

linearly with LAI because of the compensating effect of soil evaporation at low and light restrictions at high LAI (Kelliher et al., 1995). Response of $r_{s,ref}$ to drought depended on the species: the Pearson correlation between the monthly reference resistances and mean SWC was -0.45 and -0.41 for the pine-dominated SoF and KaF, respectively, but 0.29 for the spruce-dominated PaF. Similar response to drought has been observed in a southern boreal forest by Launiainen (2010) and Gao et al. (2017), while Matkala et al. (2021) observed no decrease in ET at PaF during extremely dry summers. Conductance (r_s^{-1}) to transpiration per unit needle area and its sensitivity to D are observed to be lower for spruce than for pine (Lagergren and Lindroth, 2002), which was demonstrated by the LAI-scaled $r_{s,ref}$ determined at our forest sites.

For many species, it has been observed for the parameters of Eq. (8) that $m \times r_{s,ref} \approx 0.6$ (Oren et al., 1999). The lowest mean values of this product at SoM and PaM can be explained by their high moss coverage and high water table, respectively, whereas at KaM the vegetation on the drier strings responded in a manner similar to the forest sites. Contrary to Launiainen (2010), we observed that $r_{s,ref}$ varied less on a monthly scale (average coefficient of variation 0.21) than $m \times r_{s,ref}$ (0.68).

At all sites, the bulk surface resistance (r_s) dominated over the aerodynamic resistance (r) most of the time and thus acted as the limiting factor for ET (Fig. 9). This is also evident from the correlation between the decoupling factor (Ω) and the resistances: in both mires and forests on average, the absolute correlation of Ω to r_s was higher than to r , -0.74 and -0.70 vs. 0.20 and 0.36 , respectively. The mires were more decoupled from the atmosphere than the forests because of their lower z_0 and thus weaker turbulent mixing. The highest Ω was observed at

Figure 9: Monthly median daytime (9:30–14:30 LT) aerodynamic and bulk surface resistance. The markers show medians over all years while the error bars span their 95 % confidence intervals. Right-hand side y-axes show the median decoupling factor values with 95 % c.i.

458 KaM with the lowest z_0 despite the higher average wind speeds (Table 1). Alekseychik et al. (2018) reported
 459 mean May–October Ω of 0.39 and 0.40 for two southern boreal fens. Our results indicate somewhat stronger
 460 ecosystem–atmosphere decoupling, possibly indicating less water-stressed conditions at our sites when the moss
 461 surface dries increasing r_s (Runkle et al., 2014). Conversely, lower Ω values at the forested sites indicate that
 462 stomatal control was a more important limiting factor to E , which in part explains the differences in β and EF
 463 among them. In the forests during summer, there were also days with a high Ω (Fig. 7d) corresponding mostly to
 464 a low r_s due to a low D (Fig. 8), whereas r usually remained low.

465 3.4 Surface temperature and its sensitivity

466 Surface temperature offset (T_s offset), i.e. the difference between T_s and the air temperature aloft, is an indicator
 467 of how an ecosystem modifies its ambient conditions, and it also helps us to compare sites with different ambient
 468 temperatures. In all areas, T_s offset during daytime in spring, summer and autumn was higher in the mires than in
 469 the forests, and the difference increased towards north in spring and summer (Fig. 10). The increase in T_s offset can
 470 be explained in part by the decrease in mean air temperatures towards the north. During summer days, the mires
 471 created warm microclimates close to their surfaces, which is also indicated by their higher decoupling factor (Ω),
 472 while their nighttime T_s dropped more below the surrounding air than over the forests (Fig. F.8). During spring,
 473 there was high variation in T_s offset in the mires, which is connected to the high variation of albedo due to different
 474 snow melt timing between years (Figs. 6a–6c). The higher z_0 and consequently lower r of the forests indicate more
 475 efficient exchange of energy between the surface and the atmosphere than in the mires, which explain the lower
 476 T_s offsets in the forests during summer (Fig. 10) despite the higher average net radiation (Fig. 2c). Evaporative
 477 cooling is an important controller of the surface temperature, but in the mires its effect can be limited by the

Figure 10: Distributions of surface temperature offset. The numbers above the the boxes show p -values for statistical significance difference between the two ecosystem types in an area.

478 high r compared to the forests, despite the higher EF (Fig. 5h). During the winter months, the difference in T_s
 479 offset was inverted and the mires were cooler than the forests. This can be explained by their much higher albedo
 480 (Figs. 6a–6c).

481 Deforestation at latitudes north of 45°N has been shown to lead to local cooling with the greatest contribution
 482 from the increased albedo, even though the reduced aerodynamic roughness generates a warming effect (Lee et al.,
 483 2011). In the case of restoration of drained and afforested wetlands, for which our forest–mire pairs could provide
 484 relevant information on the resulting SEB changes, also the changes in plant functional types and wetness, which
 485 affect r_s , should be taken into consideration. Helbig et al. (2020) found that the surface properties of boreal
 486 peatlands lead to lower afternoon temperatures than in the forests at similar latitudes, with contributions from both
 487 radiative and non-radiative effects. However, also opposite effects have been reported, suggesting local cooling due
 488 to peatland forestation, which results from increased evapotranspiration (Gao et al., 2014). Annual temperature
 489 effects should be studied with gap-filled data, but our results in Fig. 10 give indication that the sign of T_s change
 490 depends on the season.

491 The average surface temperatures were much more sensitive to changes in the surface resistance (r_s) than to
 492 changes in the aerodynamic resistance (r) within their plausible ranges at all sites and during all seasons, especially
 493 if r_s was combined with high r (Figs. 11a and 12). Changes in r are associated with changes in turbulence resulting
 494 from altered wind speeds or stability, assuming no sudden changes in the surface roughness length. In the long
 495 term, changes to the wind regime are possible due to the ongoing climate change, but there is uncertainty on the
 496 magnitude and direction, and annual variability overall is large (Laurila et al., 2021; Ruosteenoja and Jylhä, 2021).
 497 Changes in r_s could be due to gradual changes in hydrology (Ruosteenoja et al., 2018; Ruosteenoja and Jylhä,

Figure 11: Change in mean daytime (9:30–14:30) surface temperature in spring (April, May) when time-averages of the two variables shown on the x- and y-axes were scaled to new values. Triangle markers on the axes indicate the original time-averages.

2021) and vegetation, or they could result from the more direct response of the stomata to, e.g. drought or changes in ambient humidity. The mires were more sensitive to changes in r_s due to their generally higher r and thus more limited vertical transport of heat. SoM is distinguished as more sensitive to changes in r_s , explained by its higher EF (Fig. 5h) and higher decoupling during summer (Fig. 9). A notable exception among the forest sites was PaF, whose T_s was more sensitive to changes in r at high r_s values than the T_s of the other two forests during summer.

Scaling the mean springtime albedo (α) within its plausible range resulted in bigger changes in T_s in the mires than in the forests (Fig. 11b). Changes in α could be related to changes in snow cover duration or patchiness or changes in vegetation characteristics, e.g. deforestation due to logging or forest fires (Kinnunen et al., 2024) and shrubification of mire and tundra ecosystems (Landhausser and Wein, 1993; Mekonnen et al., 2021). In the mires, a high α was related to a low aerodynamic roughness (Fig. 6) and, consequently, high r , and vice versa, which defines the plausible combinations of α and r in the figure. In the forests, r is not connected to α in the same way, and T_s was less sensitive to changes in α .

Despite increased winter precipitation, increasing temperatures will likely cause earlier snowmelt in spring during the 21st century (Räisänen and Eklund, 2012). A dramatic difference between the mires and the forests can be seen in the T_s changes induced by snowmelt and snowfall timing, which were simulated by shifting the α time series (Fig. 13a). Compared to the snowmelt in spring, T_s during autumn was much less sensitive to the timing of the start of the snow accumulation (Fig. 13b). This is mostly due to the very limited amount of sunlight during this time of year, whereas there is ample radiative energy available during a usual snowmelt period (cf. net radiation in Fig. 4). There was also more inter-annual variation in the autumn, whereas the snowmelt happened rapidly during May at all the sites studied here (Figs. 6a–6c). However, the snow cover affects other surface properties in addition to α , such as the aerodynamic roughness and evaporation from the soil. Roughness was not included as a variable in the parametrised SEB equation (11), but it is included in r (Eq. (7)), which includes also the atmospheric wind

Figure 12: Change in mean daytime (9:30–14:30) surface temperature in summer (July, August; a) and autumn (October, November; b) when time-averages of aerodynamic and bulk surface resistances were scaled to new values shown on the x- and y-axes, respectively. Triangle markers on the axes indicate the original time-averages.

Figure 13: Change in mean daytime (9:30–14:30) surface temperature in spring (April, May; a) and autumn (October, November; b) when the average air temperature was scaled to value on the x-axis and albedo was shifted by number of days shown on the y-axis. Triangle markers on the axes indicate the original temperature time-averages.

520 forcing. In northern Europe, the earlier melt of snow and frost are connected to soil drying mainly during spring
 521 (Ruosteenoja et al., 2018). Thus, in terms of SEB, the warming climate affects many aspects of the intense spring
 522 of the northern boreal ecosystems, but likely not so much during the autumn.

523 The sensitivity of T_s to heat storage changes (not shown) was negligible compared to the other variables, as
 524 the magnitudes of the storage fluxes were very small compared to the other SEB components. Increase in ambient
 525 humidity led to small increases in T_s at the mire sites but not in the forests, where evaporative cooling is mostly
 526 controlled by the vegetation (not shown). Solar radiation is projected to increase in northern Finland during
 527 summer and autumn due to climate change (Ruuhela et al., 2023). A 5% increase in S_d in June–September would
 528 lead to approximately 0.5°C increase in the T_s in the mires and somewhat less in the forests (Fig. F.11).

529 Overall, the sensitivity of T_s to meteorological drivers was small compared to those induced by changes in the
 530 surface properties discussed above. An exception is the ambient air temperature for which T_s was very sensitive

531 (Figs. 13a and 13b). However, because the air temperature measurement heights were relatively low (Table 2), they
532 merely represent the surface layer above which there still exists a temperature gradient driving the flux of sensible
533 heat. The results indicate that the studied ecosystems are somewhat resilient to the changes in their atmospheric
534 forcing but less so to the changes in their biophysical properties.

535 **4 Conclusions**

536 It is important to understand the SEB of boreal ecosystems that face the consequences of climate change with
537 amplified warming in the northern latitudes. Despite the warming climate, the radiation conditions will not change
538 as much and the expected outcome will be a new kind of high-latitude climate: warmer but still characterised by
539 large annual variation in the day length.

540 We analysed in-situ SEB measurement data from three pristine mires and three unmanaged forests in North
541 Finland representing northern boreal ecosystems. There were no differences in the daily available energy between
542 the studied sites and similar ecosystems in the southern boreal zone in July–August, because the long polar days
543 counterbalance the effect of decreasing radiation intensity towards the north. However, the lower spring and autumn
544 temperatures in the north lead to a more pronounced seasonal cycle of energy partitioning between sensible and
545 latent heat. Compared to areas with continuous permafrost, higher surface temperatures lead to more efficient
546 radiative cooling and, consequently, lower net radiation during late spring and early summer. Mires with lower
547 and more sparse vegetation are more decoupled from the atmospheric surface layer above them than forests and
548 thus warm microclimates are created close to their surfaces. Decoupling can also happen in forests during humid
549 conditions when transpiration is not limited by the vegetation.

550 Surface temperature offset increases towards the north as ambient air is cooler underlining the importance
551 of ecosystems as modifiers of their microclimate. The surface temperature in the studied ecosystems is more
552 resilient to changes in its meteorological drivers than to changes in the biophysical properties of ecosystems, which
553 was seen as higher sensitivities to the surface properties. Climate change affects both the drivers and physical
554 surface properties, such as albedo, and our analysis on the timing of snowmelt and snowfall is an example of this:
555 The timing of snowmelt affects the mean springtime surface temperatures mostly in the mire ecosystems, where
556 vegetation is low. During autumn, the timing of snow accumulation is less important since there is less radiative
557 energy available.

558 The current results are important for understanding the specific characteristics of the SEB of northern boreal
559 ecosystems and can provide valuable information for e.g. ecosystem process modelling. Furthermore, the results
560 help to understand how SEB would respond to land cover and land management changes in similar ecosystems,
561 and how this will lead to changes in their local climates. Restoration of drained and afforested peatlands is an
562 example of possible future land use changes. The current results lay grounds to future studies that aim at attributing

563 the changes in SEB to the changes in the surface biophysical properties, helping understand the implications of
564 ecosystem restoration from the SEB point of view.

565 **Author contributions**

566 **E. Rinne:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review
567 & editing. **J.-P. Tuovinen:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Supervision, Writing
568 – review & editing. **A. Lohila:** Funding acquisition, Investigation, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **M. Aurela:**
569 Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing
570 – review & editing.

571 **Data availability**

572 Flux and meteorological measurement data for SoF (from 1 Jan 2023; Aurela et al., 2024) and KeF (from 1 Jan 2018; Laurila
573 et al., 2024) are available through the ICOS Carbon Portal. Fluxes for KaM (years 2000–2008) are available through the
574 European Fluxes Database Cluster (<https://www.europe-fluxdata.eu>). Other data are available upon request.

575 **Acknowledgments**

576 The work of E. Rinne, J.-P. Tuovinen and M. Aurela has received funding from the Research Council of Finland, project
577 ‘Quantifying the potential of boreal peatland rewetting for climate change mitigation (RESPEAT)’, grant no. 341752. E. Rinne
578 has received funding from the Research Council of Finland, project ‘Atmosphere and Climate Competence Center (ACCC)’,
579 grant no. 357904. The work of A. Lohila has been supported by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Framework Programme
580 for Research and Innovation, project ‘WET HORIZONS - upgrading knowledge and solutions to fast-track wetland restoration
581 across Europe’, project id 101056848. The authors also acknowledge support from the Finnish Ministry of Transport and
582 Communications through the Integrated Carbon Observing System (ICOS) Finland.

583 The authors would like to thank the personnel at the Finnish Meteorological Institute involved in the measurements and
584 data processing: Tuomas Laurila, Juha Hatakka, Juuso Rainne, Sami Suopajarvi and Timo Mäkelä. Henriikka Vekuri at FMI
585 is thanked for her perceptive comments on the penultimate version of the manuscript.

586 **References**

- 587 Alekseychik, Pavel et al. (2018). ‘Surface Energy Exchange in Pristine and Managed Boreal Peatlands’. In: *Mires Peat* 21,
588 pp. 1–26. doi: 10.19189/MaP.2018.OMB.333.
- 589 Aurela, Mika, Hermanni Aaltonen, Juha Hatakka, Tuomas Laurila, Annalea Lohila, Timo Mäkelä, Milja Männikkö, Juuso
590 Rainne, Sami Suopajarvi, Juha-Pekka Tuovinen and Samu Varjonen (2024). *ETC L2 Fluxes, Sodankyla, 2022-12-31–2024-*
591 *09-30*. URL: <https://hdl.handle.net/11676/FjC6kl6dbrvFwZigohzBSxBb>.

- 592 Aurela, Mika, Tuomas Laurila and Juha-Pekka Tuovinen (2001). 'Seasonal CO₂ Balances of a Subarctic Mire'. In: *J. Geophys.*
593 *Res.* 106.D2, pp. 1623–1637. doi: 10.1029/2000JD900481.
- 594 Aurela, Mika, Annalea Lohila, Juha-Pekka Tuovinen, Juha Hatakka, Timo Penttilä and Tuomas Laurila (2015). 'Carbon Dioxide
595 and Energy Flux Measurements in Four Northern-Boreal Ecosystems at Pallas'. In: *Boreal Environ. Res.* 20.4, pp. 455–473.
- 596 Aurela, Mika, Annalea Lohila, Juha-Pekka Tuovinen, Juha Hatakka, Terhi Riutta and Tuomas Laurila (2009). 'Carbon Dioxide
597 Exchange on a Northern Boreal Fen'. In: *Boreal Environ. Res.* 14.4, pp. 699–710.
- 598 Aurela, Mika, Juha-Pekka Tuovinen and Tuomas Laurila (1998). 'Carbon Dioxide Exchange in a Subarctic Peatland Ecosystem
599 in Northern Europe Measured by the Eddy Covariance Technique'. In: *J. Geophys. Res.* 103.D10, pp. 11289–11301. doi:
600 10.1029/98JD00481.
- 601 Blanken, P. D., T. A. Black, P. C. Yang, H. H. Neumann, Z. Nestic, R. Staebler, G. den Hartog, M. D. Novak and X. Lee (1997).
602 'Energy Balance and Canopy Conductance of a Boreal Aspen Forest: Partitioning Overstory and Understory Components'.
603 In: *J. Geophys. Res. Atmospheres* 102.D24, pp. 28915–28927. doi: 10.1029/97JD00193.
- 604 Bolton, David (1980). 'The Computation of Equivalent Potential Temperature'. In: *Mon. Weather Rev.* 108.7, pp. 1046–1053.
605 doi: 10.1175/1520-0493(1980)108<1046:TCOEPT>2.0.CO;2.
- 606 Chapin, F. S. et al. (2000). 'Arctic and Boreal Ecosystems of Western North America as Components of the Climate System'.
607 In: *Glob. Change Biol.* 6.S1, pp. 211–223. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-2486.2000.06022.x.
- 608 Charuchittipan, Doojdao, Wolfgang Babel, Matthias Mauder, Jens-Peter Leps and Thomas Foken (2014). 'Extension of the
609 Averaging Time in Eddy-Covariance Measurements and Its Effect on the Energy Balance Closure'. In: *Boundary-Layer*
610 *Meteorol* 152.3, pp. 303–327. doi: 10.1007/s10546-014-9922-6.
- 611 Cui, Wenhui and Ting Fong May Chui (2019). 'Temporal and Spatial Variations of Energy Balance Closure across FLUXNET
612 Research Sites'. In: *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 271, pp. 12–21. doi: 10.1016/j.agrformet.2019.02.026.
- 613 De Roo, Frederik and Matthias Mauder (2018). 'The Influence of Idealized Surface Heterogeneity on Virtual Turbulent Flux
614 Measurements'. In: *Atmospheric Chem. Phys.* 18.7, pp. 5059–5074. doi: 10.5194/acp-18-5059-2018.
- 615 Dyer, A. J. and B. B. Hicks (1970). 'Flux-Gradient Relationships in the Constant Flux Layer'. In: *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.* 96.410,
616 pp. 715–721. doi: 10.1002/qj.49709641012.
- 617 Eaton, Andrea K., Wayne R. Rouse, Peter M. Lafleur, Philip Marsh and Peter D. Blanken (2001). 'Surface Energy Balance of
618 the Western and Central Canadian Subarctic: Variations in the Energy Balance among Five Major Terrain Types'. In: *J.*
619 *Clim.* 14.17, pp. 3692–3703. doi: 10.1175/1520-0442(2001)014<3692:SEBOTW>2.0.CO;2.
- 620 Eugster, Werner, Wayne R Rouse, Roger A. Pielke Sr, Joseph P. Mcfadden, Dennis D Baldocchi, Timothy G. F Kittel, F. Stuart
621 Chapin III, Glen E. Liston, Pier Luigi Vidale, Eugene Vaganov and Scott Chambers (2000). 'Land–Atmosphere Energy
622 Exchange in Arctic Tundra and Boreal Forest: Available Data and Feedbacks to Climate'. In: *Glob. Change Biol.* 6.S1,
623 pp. 84–115. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-2486.2000.06015.x.
- 624 Foken, Thomas (2008). 'The Energy Balance Closure Problem: An Overview'. In: *Ecol. Appl.* 18.6, pp. 1351–1367. doi:
625 10.1890/06-0922.1.
- 626 Gao, Y., T. Markkanen, L. Backman, H. M. Henttonen, J.-P. Pietikäinen, H. M. Mäkelä and A. Laaksonen (2014). 'Biogeophys-
627 ical Impacts of Peatland Forestation on Regional Climate Changes in Finland'. In: *Biogeosciences* 11.24, pp. 7251–7267.
628 doi: 10.5194/bg-11-7251-2014.

629 Gao, Yao, Tiina Markkanen, Mika Aurela, Ivan Mammarella, Tea Thum, Aki Tsuruta, Huiyi Yang and Tuula Aalto (2017).
630 'Response of Water Use Efficiency to Summer Drought in a Boreal Scots Pine Forest in Finland'. In: *Biogeosciences* 14.18,
631 pp. 4409–4422. doi: 10.5194/bg-14-4409-2017.

632 Garratt, J. R. (1994). *The Atmospheric Boundary Layer*. Cambridge Atmospheric and Space Science Series. Cambridge:
633 Cambridge university press. ISBN: 978-0-521-46745-2.

634 Graf, Alexander, Anneke van de Boer, Arnold Moene and Harry Vereecken (2014). 'Intercomparison of Methods for the
635 Simultaneous Estimation of Zero-Plane Displacement and Aerodynamic Roughness Length from Single-Level Eddy-
636 Covariance Data'. In: *Bound.-Layer Meteorol.* 151.2, pp. 373–387. doi: 10.1007/s10546-013-9905-z.

637 Graveline, Vincent, Manuel Helbig, Gabriel Hould Gosselin, Haley Alcock, Matteo Detto, Branden Walker, Philip Marsh and
638 Oliver Sonntag (2024). 'Surface-Atmosphere Energy Exchanges and Their Effects on Surface Climate and Atmospheric
639 Boundary Layer Characteristics in the Forest-Tundra Ecotone in Northwestern Canada'. In: *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 350,
640 p. 109996. doi: 10.1016/j.agrformet.2024.109996.

641 Haverd, Vanessa, Matthias Cuntz, Ray Leuning and Heather Keith (2007). 'Air and Biomass Heat Storage Fluxes in a Forest
642 Canopy: Calculation within a Soil Vegetation Atmosphere Transfer Model'. In: *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 147.3–4, pp. 125–139.
643 doi: 10.1016/j.agrformet.2007.07.006.

644 Heiskanen, Lauri, Juha Pekka Tuovinen, Aleksii Räsänen, Tarmo Virtanen, Sari Juutinen, Annalea Lohila, Timo Penttilä, Maiju
645 Linkosalmi, Juha Mikola, Tuomas Laurila and Mika Aurela (2021). 'Carbon Dioxide and Methane Exchange of a Patterned
646 Subarctic Fen during Two Contrasting Growing Seasons'. In: *Biogeosciences* 18.3, pp. 873–896. doi: 10.5194/bg-18-873-
647 2021.

648 Heiskanen, Lauri, Juha-Pekka Tuovinen, Henriikka Vekuri, Aleksii Räsänen, Tarmo Virtanen, Sari Juutinen, Annalea Lohila,
649 Juha Mikola and Mika Aurela (2023). 'Meteorological Responses of Carbon Dioxide and Methane Fluxes in the Terrestrial
650 and Aquatic Ecosystems of a Subarctic Landscape'. In: *Biogeosciences* 20.3, pp. 545–572. doi: 10.5194/bg-20-545-2023.

651 Helbig, Manuel et al. (2020). 'The Biophysical Climate Mitigation Potential of Boreal Peatlands during the Growing Season'.
652 In: *Environ. Res. Lett.* 15.10, p. 104004. doi: 10.1088/1748-9326/abab34.

653 Ingwersen, J., K. Steffens, P. Högy, K. Warrach-Sagi, D. Zhunusbayeva, M. Poltoradnev, R. Gäbler, H. -D. Wizemann, A.
654 Fangmeier, V. Wulfmeyer and T. Streck (2011). 'Comparison of Noah Simulations with Eddy Covariance and Soil Water
655 Measurements at a Winter Wheat Stand'. In: *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 151.3, pp. 345–355. doi: 10.1016/j.
656 agrformet.2010.11.010.

657 Jarvis, P. G. and K. G. McNaughton (1986). 'Stomatal Control of Transpiration: Scaling Up from Leaf to Region'. In: *Advances*
658 *in Ecological Research*. Ed. by A. MacFadyen and E. D. Ford. Vol. 15. Academic Press, pp. 1–49. doi: 10.1016/S0065-
659 2504(08)60119-1.

660 Jokinen, Pauli, Pentti Pirinen, Juho-Pekka Kaukoranta, Antti Kangas, Pekka Alenius, Patrick Eriksson, Milla Johansson and
661 Sofia Wilkman (2021). *Climatological and oceanographic statistics of Finland 1991–2020*. Reports 2021:8. Helsinki,
662 Finland: Finnish Meteorological Institute, p. 169. URL: <https://helda.helsinki.fi/handle/10138/336063> (visited on
663 19/04/2023).

- 664 Juang, Jehn Yih, Gabriel Katul, Mario Siqueira, Paul Stoy and Kimberly Novick (2007). 'Separating the Effects of Albedo
665 from Eco-Physiological Changes on Surface Temperature along a Successional Chronosequence in the Southeastern United
666 States'. In: *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 34.21, pp. 1–5. doi: 10.1029/2007GL031296.
- 667 Kelliher, F.M., R. Leuning, M.R. Raupach and E.-D. Schulze (1995). 'Maximum Conductances for Evaporation from Global
668 Vegetation Types'. In: *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 73.1–2, pp. 1–16. doi: 10.1016/0168-1923(94)02178-M.
- 669 Kinnunen, Outi, Leif Backman, Juha Aalto, Tuula Aalto and Tiina Markkanen (2024). 'Projected Changes in Forest Fire
670 Season, the Number of Fires, and Burnt Area in Fennoscandia by 2100'. In: *Biogeosciences* 21.21, pp. 4739–4763. doi:
671 10.5194/bg-21-4739-2024.
- 672 Lafleur, Peter M. (2008). 'Connecting Atmosphere and Wetland: Energy and Water Vapour Exchange'. In: *Geogr. Compass*
673 2.4, pp. 1027–1057. doi: 10.1111/j.1749-8198.2007.00132.x.
- 674 Lagergren, Fredrik and Anders Lindroth (2002). 'Transpiration Response to Soil Moisture in Pine and Spruce Trees in Sweden'.
675 In: *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 112.2, pp. 67–85. doi: 10.1016/S0168-1923(02)00060-6.
- 676 Landhausser, Simon M. and Ross W. Wein (1993). 'Postfire Vegetation Recovery and Tree Establishment at the Arctic Treeline:
677 Climate-Change-Vegetation-Response Hypotheses'. In: *J. Ecol.* 81.4, pp. 665–672. doi: 10.2307/2261664.
- 678 Larsen, James A. (1980). *The Boreal Ecosystem*. New York: Academic Press. ISBN: 978-0-12-436880-4.
- 679 Launiainen, S. (2010). 'Seasonal and Inter-Annual Variability of Energy Exchange above a Boreal Scots Pine Forest'. In:
680 *Biogeosciences* 7.12, pp. 3921–3940. doi: 10.5194/bg-7-3921-2010.
- 681 Laurila, Terhi K., Victoria A. Sinclair and Hilppa Gregow (2021). 'Climatology, Variability, and Trends in near-Surface Wind
682 Speeds over the North Atlantic and Europe during 1979–2018 Based on ERA5'. In: *Int. J. Climatol.* 41.4, pp. 2253–2278.
683 doi: 10.1002/joc.6957.
- 684 Laurila, Tuomas, Hermanni Aaltonen, Mika Aurela, Juha Hatakka, Juuso Rainne and Sami Suopajarvi (2024). *Fluxnet Product,*
685 *Kenttarova, 2017-12-31–2023-12-31*. URL: <https://hdl.handle.net/11676/17j8rcc51ZGWykv6NrxJE>.
- 686 Lee, Xuhui (2018). *Fundamentals of Boundary-Layer Meteorology*. Springer Atmospheric Sciences. Springer. 1-206. ISBN:
687 978-3-319-60851-8.
- 688 Lee, Xuhui et al. (2011). 'Observed Increase in Local Cooling Effect of Deforestation at Higher Latitudes'. In: *Nature* 479.7373,
689 pp. 384–387. doi: 10.1038/nature10588.
- 690 Li, Dan and Liang Wang (2019). 'Sensitivity of Surface Temperature to Land Use and Land Cover Change-Induced Biophysical
691 Changes: The Scale Issue'. In: *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 46.16, pp. 9678–9689. doi: 10.1029/2019GL084861.
- 692 Liao, Weilin, Angela J. Rigden and Dan Li (2018). 'Attribution of Local Temperature Response to Deforestation'. In: *J.*
693 *Geophys. Res. Biogeosciences* 123.5, pp. 1572–1587. doi: 10.1029/2018JG004401.
- 694 Linkosalmi, Maiju et al. (2016). 'Digital Photography for Assessing the Link between Vegetation Phenology and CO₂ Exchange
695 in Two Contrasting Northern Ecosystems'. In: *Geosci. Instrum. Methods Data Syst.* 5.2, pp. 417–426. doi: 10.5194/gi-5-
696 417-2016.
- 697 Lohila, Annalea et al. (2016). 'Large Contribution of Boreal Upland Forest Soils to a Catchment-Scale CH₄ Balance in a Wet
698 Year'. In: *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 43.6, pp. 2946–2953. doi: 10.1002/2016GL067718.

699 Maanavilja, Liisa, Terhi Riutta, Mika Aurela, Minna Pulkkinen, Tuomas Laurila and Eeva-Stiina Tuittila (2011). ‘Spatial
700 Variation in CO₂ Exchange at a Northern Aapa Mire’. In: *Biogeochemistry* 104.1, pp. 325–345. DOI: 10.1007/s10533-010-
701 9505-7.

702 Matkala, L., L. Kulmala, P. Kolari, M. Aurela and J. Bäck (2021). ‘Resilience of Subarctic Scots Pine and Norway Spruce
703 Forests to Extreme Weather Events’. In: *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 296, p. 108239. DOI: 10.1016/j.agrformet.
704 2020.108239.

705 Mauder, Matthias, Matthias Cuntz, Clemens Drüe, Alexander Graf, Corinna Rebmann, Hans Peter Schmid, Marius Schmidt
706 and Rainer Steinbrecher (2013). ‘A Strategy for Quality and Uncertainty Assessment of Long-Term Eddy-Covariance
707 Measurements’. In: *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 169, pp. 122–135. DOI: 10.1016/j.agrformet.2012.09.006.

708 Mauder, Matthias and Thomas Foken (2004). *Quality Control of Eddy Covariance Measurements*. University of Bayreuth. URL:
709 http://gaia.agraria.unitus.it/Quality_flags_definition.pdf (visited on 19/01/2023).

710 Mauder, Matthias, Martin Jung, Paul Stoy, Jacob Nelson and Luise Wanner (2024). ‘Energy Balance Closure at FLUXNET
711 Sites Revisited’. In: *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 358, p. 110235. DOI: 10.1016/j.agrformet.2024.110235.

712 Mekonnen, Zelalem A et al. (2021). ‘Arctic Tundra Shrubification: A Review of Mechanisms and Impacts on Ecosystem Carbon
713 Balance’. In: *Environ. Res. Lett.* 16.5, p. 053001. DOI: 10.1088/1748-9326/abf28b.

714 Oren, R., J. S. Sperry, G. G. Katul, D. E. Pataki, B. E. Ewers, N. Phillips and K. V. R. Schäfer (1999). ‘Survey and Synthesis
715 of Intra- and Interspecific Variation in Stomatal Sensitivity to Vapour Pressure Deficit’. In: *Plant Cell Environ.* 22.12,
716 pp. 1515–1526. DOI: 10.1046/j.1365-3040.1999.00513.x.

717 Pang, Yuwen, Aleksí Räsänen, Teemu Juselius-Rajamäki, Mika Aurela, Sari Juutinen, Minna Väiliranta and Tarmo Virtanen
718 (2023). ‘Upscaling Field-Measured Seasonal Ground Vegetation Patterns with Sentinel-2 Images in Boreal Ecosystems’.
719 In: *Int. J. Remote Sens.* 44.14, pp. 4239–4261. DOI: 10.1080/01431161.2023.2234093.

720 Papale, D., M. Reichstein, M. Aubinet, E. Canfora, C. Bernhofer, W. Kutsch, B. Longdoz, S. Rambal, R. Valentini, T. Vesala
721 and D. Yakir (2006). ‘Towards a Standardized Processing of Net Ecosystem Exchange Measured with Eddy Covariance
722 Technique: Algorithms and Uncertainty Estimation’. In: *Biogeosciences* 3.4, pp. 571–583. DOI: 10.5194/bg-3-571-2006.

723 Pastorello, Gilberto et al. (2020). ‘The FLUXNET2015 Dataset and the ONEFlux Processing Pipeline for Eddy Covariance
724 Data’. In: *Sci. Data* 7.1, p. 225. DOI: 10.1038/s41597-020-0534-3.

725 Peräkylä, Otso, Erkkä Rinne, Ekaterina Ezhova, Anna Lintunen, Annalea Lohila, Juho Aalto, Mika Aurela, Pasi Kolari and
726 Markku Kulmala (2025). ‘Comparison of Shortwave Radiation Dynamics between Boreal Forest and Open Peatland Pairs
727 in Southern and Northern Finland’. In: *Biogeosciences* 22.1, pp. 153–179. DOI: 10.5194/bg-22-153-2025.

728 Pirinen, Pentti, Henriikka Simola, Juha Aalto, Juho-Pekka Kaukoranta, Pirkko Karlsson and Reija Ruuhela (2012). *Tilastoja*
729 *Suomen Ilmastosta 1981–2010*. Reports 2012:1. Helsinki, Finland: Finnish Meteorological Institute. URL: [https://helda.
730 helsinki.fi/items/a6d2e07c-e25a-498e-81e0-b29968e3bc55](https://helda.helsinki.fi/items/a6d2e07c-e25a-498e-81e0-b29968e3bc55) (visited on 06/09/2024).

731 Räisänen, Jouni and Joonas Eklund (2012). ‘21st Century Changes in Snow Climate in Northern Europe: A High-Resolution
732 View from ENSEMBLES Regional Climate Models’. In: *Clim Dyn* 38.11 (11), pp. 2575–2591. DOI: 10.1007/s00382-011-
733 1076-3.

- 734 Rantanen, Mika, Alexey Yu Karpechko, Antti Lipponen, Kalle Nordling, Otto Hyvärinen, Kimmo Ruosteenoja, Timo Vihma
735 and Ari Laaksonen (2022). ‘The Arctic Has Warmed Nearly Four Times Faster than the Globe since 1979’. In: *Commun.*
736 *Earth Environ.* 3.1, pp. 1–10. doi: 10.1038/s43247-022-00498-3.
- 737 Runkle, B. R.K., C. Wille, M. Gažovič, M. Wilmking and L. Kutzbach (2014). ‘The Surface Energy Balance and Its Drivers in
738 a Boreal Peatland Fen of Northwestern Russia’. In: *J. Hydrol.* 511, pp. 359–373. doi: 10.1016/j.jhydrol.2014.01.056.
- 739 Ruosteenoja, Kimmo and Kirsti Jylhä (2021). ‘Projected Climate Change in Finland during the 21st Century Calculated from
740 CMIP6 Model Simulations’. In: *Geophysica* 56.1, pp. 39–69.
- 741 Ruosteenoja, Kimmo, Tiina Markkanen, Ari Venäläinen, Petri Räisänen and Heli Peltola (2018). ‘Seasonal Soil Moisture and
742 Drought Occurrence in Europe in CMIP5 Projections for the 21st Century’. In: *Clim Dyn* 50.3 (3), pp. 1177–1192. doi:
743 10.1007/s00382-017-3671-4.
- 744 Ruuhela, Reija, Kimmo Ruosteenoja and Kaisa Lakkala (2023). ‘Projected Changes in Incident Solar Radiation in Northern
745 Hemisphere High-Latitude Areas | Ilmastokatsaus – Ilmatieteen Laitos’. In: *FMI’s Clim. Bull. Res. Lett.* 6.1. doi: 10.35614/
746 ISSN-2341-6408-IK-2024-02-RL.
- 747 Solantie, Reijo (2005). ‘Productivity of Boreal Forests in Relation to Climate and Vegetation Zones’. In: *Boreal Environ. Res.*
748 10, pp. 275–297.
- 749 Stoy, Paul C. et al. (2013). ‘A Data-Driven Analysis of Energy Balance Closure across FLUXNET Research Sites: The Role of
750 Landscape Scale Heterogeneity’. In: *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 171–172, pp. 137–152. doi: 10.1016/j.agrformet.2012.11.004.
- 751 Stull, Roland B. (1988). *An Introduction to Boundary Layer Meteorology*. Ed. by Roland B. Stull. Vol. 13. Dordrecht: Springer
752 Netherlands. 670 pp. ISBN: 978-90-277-2769-5. doi: 10.1007/978-94-009-3027-8.
- 753 Tao, Z., J. A. Santanello, M. Chin, S. Zhou, Q. Tan, E. M. Kemp and C. D. Peters-Lidard (2013). ‘Effect of Land Cover on
754 Atmospheric Processes and Air Quality over the Continental United States – a NASA Unified WRF (NU-WRF) Model
755 Study’. In: *Atmospheric Chem. Phys.* 13.13, pp. 6207–6226. doi: 10.5194/acp-13-6207-2013.
- 756 The Meteorological Service of Canada (2024). *Canadian Climate Normals 1991-2020 Data*. URL: https://climate.weather.gc.ca/climate_normals/index_e.html (visited on 25/11/2024).
- 757
- 758 Thum, Tea, Tuula Aalto, Tuomas Laurila, Mika Aurela, Pasi Kolari and Pertti Hari (2007). ‘Parametrization of Two Pho-
759 tosynthesis Models at the Canopy Scale in a Northern Boreal Scots Pine Forest’. In: *Tellus B* 59.5, pp. 874–890. doi:
760 10.1111/j.1600-0889.2007.00305.x.
- 761 Tuhkanen, Sakari (1984). ‘A Circumboreal System of Climatic–Phytogeographical Regions’. In: *Acta Bot. Fenn.* 127, pp. 1–50.
- 762 Twine, T. E., W. P. Kustas, J. M. Norman, D. R. Cook, P. R. Houser, T. P. Meyers, J. H. Prueger, P. J. Starks and M. L. Wesely
763 (2000). ‘Correcting Eddy-Covariance Flux Underestimates over a Grassland’. In: *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*
764 103.3, pp. 279–300. doi: 10.1016/S0168-1923(00)00123-4.
- 765 Vekuri, Henriikka and Erkka Rinne (2023). *ustar_threshold*. Version 0.2. URL: https://github.com/hvekuri/ustar_threshold.
- 766 Walter, Heinrich (1985). *Vegetation of the Earth and Ecological Systems of the Geo-Biosphere*. 3d rev. and enlarged ed. Berlin:
767 Springer-Verlag. ISBN: 978-0-387-13748-3.
- 768 Wieder, R. Kelman, Dale H. Vitt and Brian W. Benscoter (2006). ‘Peatlands and the Boreal Forest’. In: *Boreal Peatland*
769 *Ecosystems*. Vol. 188. Ecological Studies. Berlin Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag.

- 770 Wilson, Kell et al. (2002). 'Energy Balance Closure at FLUXNET Sites'. In: *Agric. For. Meteorol.* FLUXNET 2000 Synthesis
771 113.1, pp. 223–243. doi: 10.1016/S0168-1923(02)00109-0.
- 772 Winckler, J., C. H. Reick, R. M. Bright and J. Pongratz (2019). 'Importance of Surface Roughness for the Local Biogeophysical
773 Effects of Deforestation'. In: *J. Geophys. Res. Atmospheres* 124.15, pp. 8605–8618. doi: 10.1029/2018JD030127.
- 774 Yu, Lingxue, Ye Liu, Jiuchun Yang, Tingxiang Liu, Kun Bu, Guangshuai Li, Yue Jiao and Shuwen Zhang (2022). 'Asymmetric
775 Daytime and Nighttime Surface Temperature Feedback Induced by Crop Greening across Northeast China'. In: *Agric. For.*
776 *Meteorol.* 325, p. 109136. doi: 10.1016/j.agrformet.2022.109136.
- 777 Zhou, Yanzhao, Matthias Sühring and Xin Li (2023). 'Evaluation of Energy Balance Closure Adjustment and Imbalance
778 Prediction Methods in the Convective Boundary Layer – A Large Eddy Simulation Study'. In: *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 333,
779 p. 109382. doi: 10.1016/j.agrformet.2023.109382.

780 A Additional details of the measurements sites

Table A.1: Start and end (if applicable, otherwise ongoing) of the measurements and used instruments

Site	Start	End	Sonic anemometer	Gas analyser
SoM	Jun 2012	—	USA-1 ^a	LI-7000 ^b
SoF	Sep 2018	—	HS-50 ^c	LI-7200 ^b
PaM	Mar 2005	—	USA-1	LI-7000
PaF	Jan 2003	—	SATI/3Sx ^d , USA-1 (from 2003-09-15)	LI-7000
KaM	Apr 1997	—	SWS-211 ^d , USA-1 (from 2007-06-29)	LI-6262 ^b , LI-7000 (from 2004-10-13)
KaF	Jun 2017	Nov 2019	USA-1	LI-7000

^a METEK Meteorologische Messtechnik GmbH, Elmshorn, Germany

^b LI-COR Environmental, Lincoln, NE, USA

^c Gill Instruments Ltd, Lymington, Hampshire, UK

^d Applied Technologies, Inc., Longmont, CO, USA

781 B Gap-filling of meteorological data

782 Meteorological measurements were gap-filled using linear interpolation (limits in Table B.2), by using measurements from
783 nearby stations or a combination of these. If no representative data were available, a linear model was fitted using best quality
784 data.

Table B.2: Linear interpolation limits for gap-filling

Variables	Limit
shortwave radiation components, net radiation, wind speed	30 min
longwave radiation components	2 h
air temperature, relative humidity, soil heat flux, WTD	3 h
soil water content	6 h
air pressure	24 h

785 Air temperature and relative humidity above the forest canopy at KaF were estimated using the sonic anemometer and
786 fast-response gas analyser measurements, respectively. Calibration values for the instruments were found using the 2-m
787 measurements at a nearby automated weather station (Inari Kaamanen, WMO 02702) using total least squares fit. Limiting the
788 data to near-neutral stability with $|\zeta| < 0.005$ to minimize the vertical temperature gradient, we found that the sonic anemometer
789 had an offset of -1.42 ± 0.03 °C assuming no span error. In unstable conditions ($\zeta < -0.1$) with adequate mixing and small
790 water vapour flux ($|E| < 0.5$ mmol m⁻² s⁻¹), the water vapour mole fraction from the gas analyser was found to be in good
791 agreement with the 2-m measurement (span 1.02 ± 0.02 , offset 0.06 ± 0.10 mmol mol⁻¹) and no correction was applied.

792 C Estimation of zero-plane displacement height

793 Following Graf et al. (2014), we compared six different methods and used the ensemble median as our final estimate. The
794 methods are based on flux-profile and flux-variance similarity with data selection criteria depending on the method. The
795 maximum z_0 was set to 30 % of vegetation height at the forest sites and 100 % in the mires except at KaM where the maximum

Figure C.1: Estimated zero-place displacement height by wind sector. Missing sectors were discarded from the data as non-representative of the ecosystem.

796 hummock height (0.8 m) was used. The plausible ranges for the displacement height were set to 10–90 % of the canopy height
 797 for the forests and from 10 % of vegetation height to z_m^{EC} for the mires. The displacement height was estimated for each 22.5°
 798 wind sector separately using all data during the summer months June–August and between 8:00 and 16:00 local time to ensure
 799 only good quality data. In some sectors, there was too little data available (mainly at KaF) to find a good value for d , and these
 800 sectors were linearly interpolated from the neighbouring sectors. Figure C.1 shows the estimated displacement height by sector
 801 for the forest sites, and their mean values are shown in Table 2.

802 For the wetland sites, none of the methods presented by Graf et al. (2014) resulted in acceptable values compared to
 803 the vegetation and microtopography characteristics of the sites. Therefore, we used values used previously in the literature
 804 (Table 2).

805 D Energy balance closure

806 EBC depended on the season and was higher during the summer months June–August (Table D.3) In the mires, the closure
 807 during summer months was 98 ± 14 % (mean \pm s.e., 33 site-years) and in the forests 82 ± 7 % (18). For wetlands and evergreen
 808 needleleaf forests, Stoy et al. (2013) reported 76 ± 13 % (7 sites, mean \pm s.d.) and 88 ± 23 % (47 sites), respectively, using the
 809 LaThuile FLUXNET database.

810 PaM stands out from the other two mires with its lower EBC. The energy imbalance cannot be fully explained by the
 811 underestimation of the turbulent fluxes. The imbalances were highest during the snow melt in May, often reaching over
 812 100 W m^{-2} (Fig. D.2). A possible explanation could involve the stream that is flowing through the measurement flux footprint
 813 area: The stream originates from a denser forested area south of PaM and most likely warms when entering the open fen. This

Table D.3: Energy balance closure (%) over full year and the summer months (JJA), mean \pm s.d. over the n years of data. At KaF, there was only one full year of data. The last column has the energy balance correction factors, mean \pm s.d. over all data.

Site	n	Full year	Summer	EBC CF
SoM	10	90 ± 19	98 ± 13	1.27 ± 0.21
PaM	2	50 ± 10	77 ± 7	1.54 ± 0.22
KaM	21	81 ± 14	100 ± 13	1.33 ± 0.24
SoF	5	61 ± 7	82 ± 3	1.46 ± 0.20
PaF	10	67 ± 3	86 ± 4	1.30 ± 0.18
KaF	3	46 ± 0	72 ± 4	1.41 ± 0.27

814 lateral heat flux not was measured, but it could be taken into account if data on the the flow rate and temperature of the stream
 815 were available. This was unfortunately out of the scope of the current study.

Figure D.2: Median daily energy imbalance by month. The error bars span 50 % of values.

816 E Sensitivity to energy balance correction

817 The sensitivity of T_s solved from Eq. (11) to possible underestimation of turbulent fluxes was estimated by allocating 0–100 %
 818 of the measured energy imbalance (y-axes of Fig. E.3) to H and $L_e E$ with varying proportions (x-axes). The total imbalance
 819 was calculated as the difference between the sum of the corrected turbulent fluxes and the original, uncorrected fluxes. At
 820 $y = 0\%$, all the imbalance is subtracted from the available energy, i.e. it can be treated as an extra storage or advection term.

821 The analysis revealed differences in T_s that were at all sites an order of magnitude smaller than its temporal variation. Only
 822 at PaM, where the EBC was the smallest, attributing the energy imbalance fully into either latent or sensible heat would have
 823 changed the surface temperatures more than 0.5°C on average. We can thus conclude that correcting the turbulent fluxes to
 824 perfect energy balance closure by maintaining the Bowen ratio has not significantly influenced the results.

Imbalance allocation between latent and sensible heat

Figure E.3: Mean difference in the modelled daytime (9:30–14:30 LT) surface temperature compared to the fully corrected energy balance (100% and imbalance distributed using the original Bowen ratio) during the summer months June, July and August. Bowen ratio decreases to the left on the x-axis and increases to the right.

825 **F Additional results**

Figure F.4: Median diurnal cycle of Bowen ratio in June–August. Shaded area shows the $\pm 95\%$ c.i..

Figure F.5: Median seasonal courses of water table depth at the mire sites during the ice-free period. The shaded areas cover 50 % of data. X-axis ticks mark the first day of the months. Positive values indicate water table above the surface.

Figure F.6: Median seasonal courses of soil water content at the forest sites. The shaded areas cover 50 % of data. X-axis ticks mark the first day of the months.

Figure F.7: Monthly median daytime (9:30–14:30 LT) albedo ($\pm 95\%$ c.i.) in the mires during the snow-free period.

Figure F.8: Median monthly surface temperature offset with error bars showing the 95 % confidence interval. Daytime is 09:30–14:30 and night 21:30–02:30 local standard time. For some sites, there were not enough good nighttime data available during some months.

Figure F.9: Distributions of ambient air temperature (left) and surface temperature (right) in June–August.

Figure F.10: Median diurnal cycle of surface temperature offset in the summer months June–August with error bars showing the 95% confidence interval.

Figure F.11: Change in mean daytime (9:30–14:30) surface temperature in July–August when time-averages of shortwave (x-axes) and longwave incoming radiation (y-axes) were scaled to new values shown on the axes. Triangle markers on the axes indicate the original time-averages.